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Annotation: *This article is effective in learning and teaching English today described methods and their use.*

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Today, the demand for the study of foreign languages in our country is growing increasing. Creating effective ways to learn and teach foreign languages today is a requirement. First of all, preschool education of children to learn foreign languages and starting from schools is somehow convenient and gives a good result, but one in my opinion, how many negative sides there are. In preschool organizations, too foreign languages are taught today. Foreign to a child who does not yet know the Uzbek language well how effective it is to teach your language. In my opinion, anchayin is a big benefit does not give. During the internship, several months and even now to schools we are visiting practice uwhun. Starting even during the internship when we enter a foreign language lesson in classes, the behavior of children and the course was we observe his passion. Today in the educational system of our country, all the prerequisites for education there are conditions. The educational process in schools is based on modern technologies in the case, it is carried out with reference to modern methods. As in the past centuries pens that can be dipped in ink, whiteboards like boards are a hobby today changed to a quill. Currently, schools have a separate class for each subject his rooms, visual aids for the lesson were beyond his ability and desire to study modern in teaching students the languages of torta oladiçet as well technologies are a great helper and a good weapon to keep students interested in the lesson can be. But without having everything you need for the lesson, the teacher will have experience or if there is a lack of methodology, the importance of all things is unfortunately no benefit does not give.

Due to the high index of cooperation with foreign partners in specialists in various fields, the demand for language learning is high in them. In modern society, foreign languages are becoming an important component of professional education. Such knowledge is learned by people, first in schools, colleges, lyceums, later in institutes, educational courses or independently, familiarizing themselves with the main sets of information that help to learn a foreign language. Today there are large collections of educational materials for people with different levels of language knowledge. Success in achieving this goal depends on the practical methods and qualifications of the teachers. The ability to use information technology and modern

teaching methods helps to quickly understand new materials.¹ by combining different methods, the teacher will be able to solve certain educational programs. In this regard, teachers and students should familiarize themselves with modern methods of teaching foreign languages. As a result, skills are formed to be able to choose the most effective methods to achieve their goals. In this case, the use of several methods of teaching and learning gives an effective result. Training is carried out in small stages and is based on the existing knowledge system of the student as the time progresses, there is an increase in innovation in every area. Different styles are also emerging in Language Teaching. When teaching English, it is good to teach step by step, based on the capacity and level of the learner, their age. In this, students are divided into groups on the basis of teaching at the initial stage, teaching at the intermediate stage, teaching at the higher stage. For each stage, a special program is developed from the teacher's side.

Modern technology unambiguously speeds up the course process and language

the learning process will not be accelerated either.^{1st} grade students today a foreign language lesson has also been introduced for. Unfortunately this was not the case when I studied.

1- if the students of the class are not yet able to speak fluently about themselves even in Uzbek chet the question arises of what can learn in the language, of course.¹-it is in a foreign language that the sins are it is not foreseen to be taught to speak, in my opinion.

In conclusion, it should be said that the teaching of the modern language is aimed at the formation of a more civilized personality, as long as it has the skills of self-analysis and systematization of new knowledge. Innovative methods are an integral part of the modernization of the entire system. With confidence, teachers can get acquainted with the most advanced approaches and subsequently combine them and achieve significant growth in the educational system using their work. Many organizations are moving to a new level using multimedia capabilities to send and receive information. The use of computers and other devices determines the success of the entire educational process.

Adequate attention should be paid to the formation of speech skills and the development of social flexibility in trainings carried out in the educational process. In addition, the success of each lesson in education largely depends on the correct Organization of training.

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5.Sh.Mirziyoyev, creating an atmosphere of innovation in the worldview of our people is the most important

it is a task.As long as there is no innovation,there will be no competitive development in any area.This

if we do not widely promote changes in the field to our people,then skills are formed in people

if we do not do the intensity of today's era, science is also a step by step with the unique achievements of technique

can't be.

6.G'.Muhammedov, U.Khojamqulov, S.Toshtemirova " in pedagogical education innovation education cluster".

7. [http: / / marifatyogdusi. uz/?p=2190](http://marifatyogdusi.uz/?p=2190)